

TYPES OF SPEECH ERRORS AND EXAMPLES IN
PSYCHOLINGUISTICS

Shodieva Gulsanam Arshiddin kizi

Uzbekistan National University, PhD student

Abstract: This article is about speech errors and examples of speech errors. And there are a lot of scientists' awesome opinions about speech errors. It is very helpful to comprehend speech errors with examples. Speech errors are made by non-damaged speakers.

Key words: word exchange, sound exchange, preservation, slip of the tongue, metathesis.

Speech error is when you say the wrong word by accident or you use the wrong name that you are talking to someone. For instance, my grandmother calls me Shokhsanam. If she was talking to me Gulsanam and she called me Shokhsanam by accident. Speech error is a mistake that people cannot realize it. Sigmund Freud viewed speech errors as a window into the unconscious mind. He believed that speech errors revealed our true inner thoughts— thoughts that we suppressed in order to be polite [1]. A normal speech rate in English is around 150 words a minute. This means that a speaker retrieves two or three words per second from an everyday vocabulary of about 30,000. What is more, they continue to do so over very extended periods of time and with remarkable accuracy (about one slip per 1000 words) [2]. Natural speech is far from perfect: it is replete with filled and unfilled hesitations and errors. A speech error is a mismatch between what we intend to say and what we actually say. This entry focuses upon a mismatch involving the sounds of the language, or slips of the tongue, and will not cover hesitations. Speech errors made by non-brain damaged speakers resemble the errors made by speakers with brain damage, and the study of both sorts of errors has revealed a great deal about how humans produce language, and about the

relation between language and the brain. This entry will focus on the speech of non-brain-damaged speakers [3].

Freud held speech errors “arise from the concurrent action – perhaps rather, the mutually opposing action – of two different intentions [4]. One of these two intentions is the meaning that the speaker consciously wishes to convey. A second, disturbing intention interferes with the conscious purpose, and the outcome of this conflicts is a slip of the tongue. It is not necessary that the speaker should be unaware of the activity of the disturbing purpose within him before it reveals it in the slip, although, as Freud states: “My interpretation carries with it the hypothesis that intentions can find expression in a speaker of the himself knows nothing, but which I am able to infer from circumstantial evidence” [5].

Each type of speech error refers to how the speech formation system works. Examples include Matthew J. Traxler gives information about speech errors. The first is semantic substitution. For example, in some people say another word when they want to say one word. For example, when you need to say what is in the picture in a short time, the cat is replaced by a rat or a dog.

Sometimes, some phonemes are produced correctly and some of them appear in the wrong position in use. This situation is called word exchanges. This is an error in which one-word switches position with another word in an utterance. For example, instead of the phrase fifty-pound bag of food, speaker may actually say “fifty-pound dog of bag food”. Sound exchange errors almost always occur when sounds are exchanged between words in the same phrase, and the vast majority involve movement of only a single phoneme from each word [6]. So, you are more likely to say That guy has fig beet, where the two target words are in the same noun phrase, than you are to say, These beet are really fig (Target: These feet are really big), where one word appears in a subject noun phrase and the other appears as part of the following verb phrase. In addition, sound exchanges almost always respect the positional constraint. That is, when sounds trade places, they almost always come

from the same part of the word, usually the first phoneme. You would almost never say *tig feeb* by mistake, as this error would violate the positional constraint [7].

Anticipation is an error in which a later sound replaces an earlier sound in an utterance. Target: *free throw* [fri: 'θrəʊ], error: [θri: 'θrəʊ].

Here is an interdental fricative replaced the labial dental fricative in an utterance, another words, brain is already anticipating having to articulate the interdental fricative before the phrase is even uttered.

Perseveration is a speech error in which an earlier sound replaces a later sound or an earlier sound simply sticks around or perseveres. Example, target: *black boxes* [blæk 'bɒksɪz], error: [blæk 'blɒksɪz]. This phrase could be mispronounced “black bloxes”, we should notice here that sound is hanging around awkwardly.

Blend is an error in which parts of two or more words are combined to yield a new word. Example, target: *great and good* [greit, gu:d] error: [greit, gru:d]. They have taken one syllable onset “gr” from the word *great* and combined it with syllable rhyme “ud” from the word *good* yielding “grud”.

Metathesis is an error in which two sounds switch positions with one another. Example, target: *milk and honey* [mɪlk hʌni], error: [hɪlk mʌni]. This could be mispronounced because, glottal fricative and bilabial nasal have switched positions. It is important that metathesis is not to be confused with metathesis as a co-articulation effect such as in the pronunciation of *ask* as *acts*. This is often a feature of some speaker’s dialect of English.

Why do these speech errors happen at all? There are a number of reasons why speaker could be tired, could be distracted or they could be multitasking. This happens when people can feel totally normal. Because, these speech errors are natural and we all do this at some point, but they do offer a very unique window into the complex processes of speech production.

References:

1. Sigmund Freud. Introduction to Psychoanalysis. – Xarkov Belgorod, 1917. P.98
2. John Field. Psycholinguistics Key concepts. – Routledge, 2004. P.283.
3. Trevor A. Harley speech errors. Psycholinguistic analysis. University of Dundee, 2006. P.1
4. Sigmund Freud. Introduction to Psychoanalysis. – Xarkov Belgorod, 1917.
5. Sigmund Freud. Introduction to Psychoanalysis. – Xarkov Belgorod, 1917.
6. Matthew J. Traxler. Introduction to Psycholinguistics. Understanding language science. - A John Wiley & Sons, Ltd., Publication, 2012. P. 52
7. Matthew J. Traxler. Introduction to Psycholinguistics. Understanding language science. - A John Wiley & Sons, Ltd., Publication, 2012. P. 54

